
**ENSURING EQUAL OPPORTUNITIES IN SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY LITERACY: FOCUS ON GENDER DISPARITY IN
SCIENCE CLASSROOM**

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Abstract

The study is a qualitative research. It is intended to sensitize our educational system on the need to create equal learning opportunities for male and female students in the classroom. A total of 240 subjects were selected randomly among junior secondary school year three students out of nine secondary schools in Ikere local government area of Ekiti State. Three groups, A, B and C were involved in the study, group A that comprised of male and female students. B comprised of male student only and C comprised of female students only. The instrument used was Integrated Science concept test (ISCT) which was administered on the population after three weeks intensive coaching. The results of pre test and post test were subjected to mean, standard deviations and analyses of covariance. The two hypotheses were rejected at 0.05 alpha level of significance. It was therefore concluded that there was a significant difference between the post test mean scores of integrated science concept test (ISCT) of male and female students in the same classroom and those in different classrooms.

INTRODUCTION

Science and technological literacy is important aspect of educational practice: however, it is far from being reached under the present circumstance bewildering science and technology education in Africa, with particular reference to Nigeria. Scientific literacy is to provide the young and old, black and white, men and women, boys and girls, able and disabled with ample and equal opportunities to acquire the necessary skills, knowledge, understanding and attitudes which would enable them to behave as functioning adults and responsible member of the society not necessarily making every one a scientist or technologist.

In the 21st century, virtually every nation would be increasingly affected by science and its applications in technology. In nearly all African countries, both formal and informal, science education through remedial or adult education programme, science museum, library and achieves and out of school science activities have been mounted for the development of scientific literacy among the populace. All these will give greater prominence to science and technology among the populace. All these will give greater prominence to science and technology in African countries. No one disputes the claim that scientific knowledge and technological education are not uniformly available to all across the country. In particular, it is generally recognized that girls and women have less interest in scientific and technological education than is the case for boys and men. (Duyilemi, 1996) the issue of under representation and under achievement of girls and women in science is being recognized. Nevertheless, there has been considerable interest in the curl-clued education Eshiwani (1987).

In a survey conducted among over five hundred, first year Australian university students, Harrison (1986) found that most students, especially those who had attended co-educational schools are preferable and led the development of more natural attitude towards the opposite sex. While Harrison (1986) admitted that the single sex schools were generally smaller, more urban and more selective than the educational schools, making comparisons difficult to interpret, she concluded that co-educational schools, at least for this selective sample, may have some advantages in fostering interactions with the opposite sex.

It has also been asserted by Gilligan (1982), Spender (1982) that boys typically attract more of teachers' attention than girls in co-educational classrooms. The issue of gender inequality in education has been identified and documented for decades, yet we find that the problem continues regardless of the many theories and

action plans that have been suggested in the past.

Curriculum education should be because our society can no longer afford to use half the potential of its population, Peitz (1990). Many models have been reported on the relationship between gender and science in schools by many researchers. Riley (1993) reported a model based on behaviours, attitude, beliefs, experience, socio-cultural and educational context of teacher and students. Also, Murphy (1996) pointed out that gender difference in science is in favour of boys and have been attributed to factors such as interaction frequently between teacher and students, time of exposure to science-related activities, curriculum contents and the exposure to science related activities, curriculum contents and the process of socialization. Although science courses are for all people who live in the modern society, gender differences still exist in science classroom. Science educators have evidence in gender difference in science, with factors such as achievement, attitude, motivation, interest, and performance behaviours.

This study is, therefore a qualitative research that intends to sensitize our need to create equal learning environments for boys and girls in science classroom.

Purpose of the study

The study is aimed at creating equal learning environment for boys and girls in science classroom.

Research Hypotheses

H₀, There is no significant difference between the post-test mean scores in integrated science concept test (ISCT) of male and female students in a separate classroom.

H₀, There is no significant difference between the post-test mean scores in integrated science concept test (ISCT) of male and female in the same classroom.

Research methods

This study is a quasi-experimental design which adopted a non randomized control group pre-test, post test design as described by Campbell and Stanley (1966). The subject for the study was 240 junior secondary school III integrated science students of three schools in Ikere local government area of Ekiti State, during the 2004/2005 session. Three groups A, B, and C were involved in this study with Group A consisting of male and female from a coeducational school taught together in a

classroom as control. Group B consisted of male students alone in a single sex school classroom as experimental group (i) and Group C consisted of female students alone in a single sex school as experimental group (ii).

Treatment and Instrumentation

One treatment with one instrument was developed for use in this study. The only treatment was the integrated science concept test (ISCT) based on an introductory course in the theory of Energy. The instrument was a multiple choice test based for the post test out of which fifteen questions were chosen as test-run in the pre-test.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

45 questions were initially constructed and then field tested. The difficulty and discriminating powers of each item were determined. Ten of the questions were too high or too low. The content of (ISCT) was assessed and corrected by four integrated science specialists, and it was certified to be adequate for the research.

The reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined by using Kuder Richardson formula (KR21) with the scores obtained from 60 students for this kind of study.

Integrated Science Concept Test (ISCT)

The ISCT was developed by the researcher. It was based on energy as dictated by the secondary schools integrated science syllabus. It contained

- The meaning of energy
- Forms or types of energy
- Transformation of energy

Procedure

The teachers involved in the study were adequately trained as to the objective of the study. Teachers of group A (male and female) students gave lectures on energy for three weeks after administering the pretest. Group A served as control for experimental groups B and C. The treatment took up simultaneously for three weeks after which the groups were exposed to post test.

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Results

The two hypotheses tested were subjected to mean, standard deviations and Analyses of covariance (ANCOVA)

Ho₁ There is no significant difference between the post-test mean scores in integrated science concept test (ISCT) of male and female students in a separate classroom.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics of pretest and post test scores in integrated science concept test of male and female students in the same classroom.

Ho₁ states it here

Group	N	Pretest		Post Test	
		XE	XO		
(A) Control	120	2.60	1.30	10.41	3.68
(B) E1	120	2.86	1.16	17.22	2.76
(C) E1	120	2.86	1.12	11.50	3.79

P<0.05 level of significance

The table above showed that the standard deviation for pretest of control group= 1.30 is less than the standard deviation of control group = 3.68, likewise the standard deviation for pretest of experiment group B = 1.16 is less than the standard deviation for post test of experimental group B = 2.76 and standard deviation for pretest of experimental group C = 3.79.

It therefore revealed that there is significant difference between the achievement of male and female students in the same classroom. It revealed that the treatment has significant affect(s) on sampled students.

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H_{o_2} There is no significant difference between the post-test mean scores in integrated science concept test (ISCT) of male and female in the same classroom.

Table 2
Descriptive statistics of pretest scores in integrated science concept text male and female students in different classroom.

Group	N	XE	Pretest	Xo	Post Test
(A) Control	120	5.54	1.37	24.00	0.77
(B) E1	120	2.60	0.67	17.19	1.53
(C) E1	120	1.52	0.81	14.90	1.27

$P < 0.05$ level of significance

At 0.05 level of significance, the table above showed that the standard deviation for pretest of control group = 1.37 is greater than the standard deviation for post test control group 0.77, likewise the standard deviation for pretest of experimental B = 0.67 is less than the standard deviation for pre-test of experimental group C = 0.81 is less than standard deviation for post test of experimental group C is 1.27, it therefore revealed that the treatment has significant effect(s) on the sample students.

Table 3
Analysis of covariance of post test scores of integrated science concept test (ISCT) of male and female students in the same classroom using pretest scores as covariance

Source	Sum of square	DF	Mean square	F-cal	Significant of F
Covariates	2321.280	1	2321.280	151.055	0.0001
Maineffects	2488.430	2	1244.215	80.966	0.0001
Explained	5470.711	3	1603.237	104.329	0.0001
Residual	5470.678	356	15.367		
Total	10280.389	359	28.636		

P<0.05 level of significance

The table showed statistical main effect of treatment on students' achievement in Integrated science, since the value of F-cal (80.966) is greater than the F-table (3.84). Therefore the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. It is therefore concluded that there was a significant difference between the post test mean scores in integrated science concept test (ISCT) of male and female students on the same classroom.

Source	Sum of square	DF	Mean square	F-cal	Significant of F
Covariates	2314.337	1	2314.337	115.198	0.0001
Maineffects	776.996	2	338.483	19.337	0.0001
Explained	3091.303	3	1033.434	51.291	0.0001
Residual	7111.94	357	20,090		
Total	10203.218	357	28.580		

P<0.05 level of significance

The table showed statistical main effect of treatment on students achievement in integrated science since the value of F-cal (19.337) is greater than the F-table (3.84) therefore the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. It is therefore concluded that there was significant difference between the post test mean scores in integrated science concept (ISCT) of male and female students in different classrooms.

DISCUSSIONS

The results showed that there was a significant difference between the post test mean scores in integrated science concept test (ISCT) of male and female students in the classroom as in the case of coeducational school and those in different classrooms. This is in line with Murphy (1996) that science mostly is in favour of boys. This was strictly attributed to factors such as interaction frequency between teacher and students, time of exposure to science related activities, curriculum contents and the process of socialization as a condition for course maintenance. Probably, this was based on the advice of Pitz (1990) to the educational world that “we need to encourage our girls because our society can no longer afford to use only half the potential of its population”. It has also been widely demonstrated in the past for example, Harrison (1986) concluded that most students especially those who have attended coeducational school are preferable and lead to a more natural attitude towards the opposite sex. While Harrison (1986) also admitted that the single-sex school visited were generally smaller, more urban and more selective than the coeducational schools, making comparisons difficult to interpret, she therefore concluded that “coeducational schooling at least for this selective sample, may have some advantages in fostering interactions with the opposite sex”. Gilligan (1982) also agreed that boys typically attract more of the teachers' attention than girls in coeducational schools/classroom.

Implications for Nigeria

From the findings, it is better to create equal learning environment for boys and girls in science classroom for the possibilities of achieving the long aspired gender equity in science and technology education in years to come.

REFERENCES

- Campbell, D.T. and Stanley H.C. (1996):** *Experimental and quasi-experimental designs for research.* Chicago. Rand-MC Nelly publishing Co.
- Duyilemi, A.N. (1996):** *A review of some current issues in Science Education: The African perspective. Research in curriculum studied (RICS). Ondo state university. Ado-Ekiti. Pp 134 141.*
- Eshiwani, G.S. (1987):** Participation of Girls in science and technology education in Kenya, Mimeo bureau of education.
- Gilligan (1982):** *In a difference voice: psychology theory and women's development.* Cambridge Ma Harvard university press.
- Harris, M.B. (1986):** Co-education and sex roles. *Australian Journal of Education*, 3, 117 131.
- Murphy, P.B. (1996):** Assessment practices and gender difference. In L.H. Parker, L.S. Rennie and Frazer (Eds). *Gender in science and mathematics.* Shorting the shadow. Boston: Kluwer.
- Peitz, W. (1993):** Can Girls plus science stereotypes equals science? *The science teacher* pp 44-49.
- Riley, D. (1993):** Gender differences in science education Building model. *Educational psychologist* 379-404.
- Spender, D. (1982):** *Invisible women: The schooling scandal.* London: writers and readers.